

Disease brief_TICK-BORNE ENCEPHALITIS (TBE)

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	<p>Tick-Borne Encephalitis (TBE) caused by Tickborne encephalitis virus (TBEV) is an arboviral flavivirus (enveloped, positive-sense, single-stranded RNA) enzootic to Eurasia and Japan. There are five known subtypes: European (TBEV-Eu), Siberian (TBEV-Sib), Far Eastern (TBEV-Fe), Himalayan (TBEV-Him), and Baikalian (TBEV-Bkl). (1)</p> <p>Tick-borne encephalitis (TBE) is transmitted by the bite of infected tick found in woodland habitats to humans, affecting the central nervous system causing fever, fatigue, headache, muscular ache and nausea and subsequently meningitis and/or encephalitis.</p>
2	Regulatory status in the EU	<p>TBE is a non-WOAH-listed disease in wildlife reported by Members to the WOAH, through the voluntary annual report (2)</p> <p>TBE is covered by Dir 2003/99/EC (in Annex I -point B – “List of zoonoses and zoonotic agents to be monitored according to the epidemiological situation”).</p>
3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	<p>For 2020 24 EU/EEA countries reported human TBE cases with the highest rates over 100 000 (>5) in Lithuania , Slovenia, Czechia, Estonia, and Latvia (3). <i>I. ricinus</i> - current known distribution map <i>I. persulcatus</i> – the current known distribution map by VectorNet could possibly facilitate future integration of these data. (4)</p>
4	Reservoir / main host	<p>Small mammals are the most important reservoir hosts for TBEV because they develop and maintain viraemia. Larger mammals and birds generally support viral maintenance indirectly by hosting ticks rather than developing a continuous viraemia. The main animal species in Europe facilitating tick-to-tick virus transmission during co-feeding are cattle (<i>Bos taurus</i>); Domestic dogs (<i>Canis lupus familiaris</i>); European mole (Talpa europaea); Foxes (<i>Vulpes</i> spp.); small ruminants (<i>Capra aegagrus hircus</i> and <i>Ovis aries</i>); Horses (<i>Equus ferus caballus</i>); Swine (<i>Sus scrofa</i>); European pine voles (<i>Microtus agrestis</i>); Corvids (<i>Corvus</i> spp.). (2)</p>

5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	Domestic and wild mammals and birds. (2)
6	Vector-borne transmission	<p>TBE virus (TBEV) is transmitted by hard ticks (7), castor bean tick (<i>Ixodes ricinus</i>) and the taiga tick (<i>I. persulcatus</i>) in Europe and Asia, respectively. <i>I. arboricola</i>, <i>gibbosus</i>, <i>hexagonus</i>, & <i>ovatus</i> less commonly transmit TBEV; <i>Dermacentor reticulatus</i>; <i>D. marginatus</i> & <i>silvarum</i> less commonly transmit TBEV; <i>Haemaphysalis concinna</i>; <i>H. intermix</i>, <i>japonica</i>, <i>longicornis</i>, & <i>punctata</i> less commonly transmit TBEV as well as <i>Hyalomma marginatum</i>.</p> <p>TBEV prevalence in ticks is highly variable based on geographic region and climate but is generally higher in adult than immature stages. Ticks acquire and transmit the virus while feeding, and infection is maintained transstadially. Transovarial transmission is possible but is suspected to be less important. (1)</p>
7	Environmental transmission	No.
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	<p>Tick bite.</p> <p>Juvenile tick stages co-feeding on the same rodent is believed to be a significant route of transmission for TBEV among ticks. Vertical transmission has been demonstrated in experimentally infected voles and their offspring; some avian species are believed to transmit TBEV transovarially. (1)</p>
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	Tick bite and unpasteurised milk and other dairy products. (5)
10	Disease indicators	There is interest in using animals (particularly livestock as well as wild ruminants such as deer) as sentinels for TBEV in the environment. (1)
11	a) Clinical signs	Sudden fever and depression in sheep, weight loss and decreased milk yield in cattle. In sheep it manifests with acute fever, ataxia and tremors before progressing to recumbency. Dogs manifest fever, behaviour changes, proprioceptive deficits, motor deficits, central vestibular disease and cranial nerve deficits. Dogs may die suddenly within days of infection. Horses develop inappetence, ataxia, muscle cramping, paralysis of the neck and forelimbs. (1)
12	b) Seroconversion	Viraemia in rodents is observed between one- and 5-days post infection; (1)

		Small mammals do not commonly show clinical signs but can develop robust, long-lasting, and specific antibody responses to infection. Because of this, there is interest in using goats and sheep as sentinels for TBEV. (1)
13	c) Other disease indicators	Decreased milk yield in cattle. (6)
14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	Nervous symptoms in dogs and horses, (6) Drop in milk yield in cattle.
15	Test systems available for infection/disease detection	Identification of the agent: 1. Reverse-transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR); Virus isolation; Immunohistochemistry (IHC). Serological tests: IgM or IgG-capture enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA): paired acute and convalescent sera for detecting seroconversion or rising titres; positive ELISA assays should be confirmed with serum neutralisation assays; Cross-reactivity with other flaviviruses can occur. Plaque reduction/serum neutralisation test (PRSN) is the "gold standard" for detection. (1)
16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Serological surveillance in small ruminants in high-risk regions; 2. Pathogen detection raw milk from domestic ruminants (cattle, sheep and goats) in high-risk regions; 3. Pathogen detection in ticks in high-risk regions (ticks dragging and flagging). <p>TBE may pose a risk for endangered wildlife species in Europe. Among wild endangered species distributed in Europe potentially infected by TBE virus (diagnosis includes direct detection of pathogen), classified according of their conservation status according (International Union for the Conservation of Nature), 33,7% species are "Near Threatened", 43,4% are "Vulnerable", 9,6% Endangered, and 13,3% Critically Endangered (CR).</p>

		GENERAL POPULATION	EXPOSED	INFECTED	INFECTIOUS	SYMPTOMATIC	GP/VD VISIT	DEAD	Component name
VECTOR-borne diseases									
Tick-borne encephalitis (TBE)	Ruminants								Serological surveillance in domestic ruminants in high-risk areas
									Pathogen detection in raw milk samples from domestic ruminants in high-risk areas
	Wild ruminants								No surveillance component specifically designed
	Rodents								No surveillance component specifically designed
	Ixodes ricinus								Pathogen detection in ticks in high-risk areas
Human								Surveillance components targetting human were not in scope	
17	Comparison of surveillance component options (main advantages/disadvantages)	<p>1. Serological surveillance in small ruminants in high-risk regions - ADVANTAGES: allows to collect blood for the research of several diseases at the same time; it allows to have the confirmation that the animal has had the disease and there has been seroconversion. DISADVANTAGES: requires resources (personnel and materials) to be completed; only useful if transmitting ticks are present.</p> <p>2. Pathogen detection in milk from ruminants - ADVANTAGES: allows to collect milk for the research of several diseases at the same time; samples can be collected from public or private veterinarians during the rutinary visits on premises. DISADVANTAGES: it may not be easy to define 7the representative sample to be collected; it could require unjustifiable economic energies; milk is easily perishable and must be transported, refrigerated; not all MS laboratories might be equipped and trained to search for TBEV on milk.</p> <p>3. Pathogen detection in ticks in high-risk regions (dragging and flagging) - ADVANTAGES: allows to sample multiple zones at the same time; allows to sample ticks of multiple species and investigate different diseases at the same time; does not require special means; detecting the virus in ticks is</p>							

		essential to confirm that an observed seroconversion in vertebrates is due to TBEV. DISADVANTAGES: not always feasible depending on the collection areas, which may be difficult to access; the costs of some types of analysis are high; does not define the exact location where the tick originated from. (7)
18	Countries which already carry out surveillance for this pathogen	Within Europe positives cases recorded are reported according to the suspected cases of disease identified (e.g., in dogs and horses) and some research is conducted at laboratories and universities at the MS level.
19	References	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1) WOAH Flavivirus (causing tick borne encephalitis) (Infection with) Technical disease card – Terrestrial Manual, 20202) WOAH about disease Tick-borne Encephalitis, 20223) Walter M, Vogelgesang JR, Rubel F, Brugger K. Tick-Borne Encephalitis Virus and Its European Distribution in Ticks and Endothermic Mammals. <i>Microorganisms</i>. 2020;8(7):1065. Published 2020 Jul 17. doi:10.3390/microorganisms80710654) Braks M, Schaffner F, Medlock JM, Berriatua E, Balenghien T, Mihalca AD, Hendrickx G, Marsboom C, Van Bortel W, Smallegange RC, Sprong H, Gossner CM, Czwienczek E, Dhollander S, Briët O and Wint W (2022) VectorNet: Putting Vectors on the Map. <i>Front. Public Health</i> 10:809763. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2022.8097635) Buczek AM, Buczek W, Buczek A, Wysokińska-Miszczuk J. Food-Borne Transmission of Tick-Borne Encephalitis Virus-Spread, Consequences, and Prophylaxis. <i>Int J Environ Res Public Health</i>. 2022 Feb 5;19(3):1812. doi: 10.3390/ijerph19031812. PMID: 35162837; PMCID: PMC8835261.6) Salat J, Ruzek D. Tick-borne encephalitis in domestic animals. <i>Acta Virol</i>. 2020;64(2):226-232. doi: 10.4149/av_2020_212. PMID: 32551790.7) TECHNICAL REPORT Field sampling methods for mosquitoes, sandflies, biting midges and ticks VectorNet project 2014–20188) Eurosurveillance - Special edition: Tick-borne encephalitis (TBE) December 20199) Johnson N, Golding M, Phipps LP. Detection of Tick-Borne Pathogens in Red Deer (<i>Cervus elaphus</i>), United Kingdom. <i>Pathogens</i>. 2021 May 23;10(6):640. doi: 10.3390/pathogens10060640. PMID: 34070977; PMCID: PMC8224737.

		10) https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/tick-borne-encephalitis/facts/factsheet
20	Additional comments	<p>Since 2012 TBE in humans is notifiable in the European Union. (8)</p> <p>No data of prevalence in animals on WAHIS Interface Platform – disease situation (Dashboard).</p> <p>UK collect blood from deer and do serosurveillance of TBEV (in combination with tick surveillance). (9)</p>